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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16599455>**A Polyphenolic Approach to Cancer Treatment: A Review on Curcumin, Quercetin, and Gallic Acid****Büşra GÜLBENLİ TÜRKÖĞLU¹**¹ Mehmet Akif Ersoy University, Institute of Health Sciences, 15000, Burdur, Türkiye
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Abstract: Cancer remains the second leading cause of death worldwide after cardiovascular diseases and continues to pose a major global health challenge due to its multifactorial etiology. In recent years, increasing attention has been given to the potential role of dietary natural compounds in the prevention and treatment of cancer. Polyphenols, which are abundant in plant-based foods such as fruits, vegetables, tea, and spices, have emerged as promising secondary metabolites with anticancer potential. These compounds exert antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-proliferative, and anti-metastatic effects, and can also modulate tumor development through epigenetic mechanisms. Polyphenols induce programmed cell death (apoptosis) in cancer cells, inhibit tumor angiogenesis, and target key signaling pathways such as MAPK, PI3K/Akt, and NF- κ B to limit cell proliferation. This review focuses on the cytotoxic, anti-proliferative, and anti-metastatic effects of selected polyphenols—curcumin, quercetin, and gallic acid—on cancer cells, as well as the underlying molecular pathways responsible for these effects. These natural compounds hold promise as less toxic agents that can complement or serve as alternatives to conventional cancer therapies.

Introduction

Cancer is one of the most serious global health challenges, ranking as the second leading cause of death worldwide after cardiovascular diseases. According to the *Global Cancer Statistics 2020* report jointly published by the American Cancer Society (ACS) and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), approximately 17 million people were affected by cancer globally in 2020. This report encompasses data from 185 countries and 36 different cancer types (Huang et al., 2009; Schiller and Lowy, 2020; Miller et al., 2020). There is compelling evidence suggesting that diet plays a critical role in the initiation and progression of this multifactorial disease, which is influenced by genetic, environmental, and lifestyle-related factors, particularly dietary habits (Briguglio et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2018).

Currently, cancer is treated using a wide range of approaches including surgery, chemotherapy, hormonal therapy, radiotherapy, immunotherapy, targeted therapies, nanotechnology, and RNA-based treatments. Chemotherapy, the dominant form of systemic therapy, operates by damaging the DNA of rapidly dividing cancer cells, thereby inhibiting their proliferation or inducing cell death. It is typically administered in short cycles at the maximum tolerated dose, followed by rest periods to allow for the recovery of healthy cells (Nurgali et al., 2018). Despite its therapeutic benefits, chemotherapy is associated with significant toxicities affecting the blood, digestive system, nervous system, liver, and kidneys. It also leads to adverse effects such as hair loss and a substantial decline in patients' quality of

life. In cases where these side effects cannot be adequately managed, dose reduction often becomes the only option. In this context, plant-derived natural compounds such as polyphenols have garnered significant interest. These substances hold promise as ideal alternatives for cancer treatment due to their potential to be more effective, safer, and less toxic when used alone or in combination with conventional therapies (Cháirez-Ramírez et al., 2021). Naturally occurring in plant-based foods such as fruits, vegetables, spices, tea, and wine, polyphenols have emerged as promising agents in cancer prevention and therapy (Fu et al., 2010; Deng et al., 2013).

Polyphenols constitute a broad class of plant-derived secondary metabolites characterized by at least one aromatic ring bearing one or more hydroxyl groups in their chemical structure (Manach et al., 2004). With over 8,000 different types identified in nature, these compounds are primarily categorized into flavonoids and phenolic acids, which account for approximately 60% and 30% of all naturally occurring polyphenols, respectively (Zhou et al., 2016). The anticancer efficacy of polyphenols is attributed to their multifaceted and complex mechanisms of action. Rather than targeting a single molecular pathway, these compounds are capable of simultaneously modulating multiple critical processes involved in cancer development and progression (Dana et al., 2022).

Phenolic compounds exert multifaceted effects on carcinogenesis, the multistep process of cancer development. On one hand, they activate cellular defense systems such as detoxifying and antioxidant enzymes; on the other hand, they suppress key signaling pathways involved in inflammation (anti-inflammatory activity) and cell proliferation. This suppression leads to cell cycle arrest and/or the induction of cell death. The anticancer effects of polyphenols are further enhanced by their ability to modulate the epigenome of cancer cells, thereby altering gene expression patterns (Briguglio et al., 2020). By preventing DNA damage caused by oxidative stress, they reduce the risk of normal cells undergoing malignant transformation (Mouria et al., 2002). Additionally, polyphenols target major signaling pathways such as MAPK, PI3K/Akt, and NF- κ B, which are crucial for uncontrolled proliferation, survival, and metastasis of cancer cells, thereby inhibiting tumor growth. Unlike healthy cells, cancer cells evade programmed cell death; polyphenols counteract this by triggering apoptosis, promoting self-destruction of malignant cells. Furthermore, they inhibit angiogenesis—the formation of new blood vessels necessary for tumor growth and dissemination—thereby restricting tumor nourishment and metastasis. Lastly, polyphenols have also been shown to exert epigenetic effects by modulating the expression of cancer-related genes (Briguglio et al., 2020; Ramirez et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2016). This review discusses the cytotoxic, anti-proliferative, and anti-metastatic effects of curcumin, quercetin, and gallic acid on cancer cells, with a particular focus on the key molecular pathways underlying these effects.

Curcumin and Its Anticancer Potential

Curcumin, the principal active component of turmeric, has attracted considerable attention due to its anticancer effects against various types of cancer. Numerous studies have demonstrated that curcumin exerts its effects through multiple mechanisms, including the inhibition of cancer cell proliferation, induction of apoptosis (programmed cell death), and prevention of metastasis (Tomeh et al., 2019).

Mechanisms of Action in Breast Cancer Treatment

In the context of breast cancer treatment—one of the most extensively studied areas regarding curcumin's broad-spectrum activity—curcumin demonstrates multifaceted therapeutic potential by targeting critical signaling pathways involved in cell survival, metastasis, and drug resistance. A key mechanism of action is its ability to overcome autocrine growth hormone (GH)-induced resistance. Curcumin achieves this by inhibiting the NF- κ B

signaling pathway, specifically by preventing the phosphorylation of the p65 protein and its binding to DNA (Coker-Gurkan et al., 2018). Moreover, under prolonged exposure, curcumin can suppress GH-induced invasion and metastasis by downregulating the expression of the miR-182-96-183 cluster (Coker-Gurkan et al., 2019). In addition, curcumin induces G2/M phase cell cycle arrest and caspase-mediated apoptosis by modulating polyamine (PA) metabolism and downregulating proteins such as cyclin B1 and Cdc2 (Berrak et al., 2016; Coker-Gurkan et al., 2018).

One of curcumin's most noteworthy clinical potentials lies in its ability to sensitize breast cancer cells to conventional chemotherapeutic agents. For instance, it has been shown to reduce the expression of flap endonuclease 1 (FEN1)—a protein implicated in cisplatin resistance—in a dose-dependent manner, thereby resensitizing cancer cells to cisplatin (Zou et al., 2018). Similarly, curcumin can reverse resistance associated with increased expression of multidrug resistance protein 1 (MDR-1) and aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 (ALDH-1), which are commonly induced by paclitaxel (PAX) treatment. Notably, the co-administration of curcumin with vitamin D3 has been demonstrated to synergistically enhance the cytotoxic effect of paclitaxel by downregulating these resistance markers (Attia, 2020).

Therapeutic Potential in Prostate Cancer

The therapeutic potential of curcumin is not limited to breast cancer; it also demonstrates promising results in other hormone-related cancers such as prostate cancer. Studies have indicated that curcumin possesses a multifaceted therapeutic capacity against prostate cancer. It has been reported to induce apoptosis (programmed cell death) in both androgen-sensitive and the more treatment-resistant androgen-independent prostate cancer cells (Dorai et al., 2000). One of the key underlying mechanisms involves curcumin's targeting of androgen metabolism and signaling pathways. While curcumin downregulates the expression of the androgen receptor (AR) (Dorai et al., 2000), it simultaneously modulates intratumoral testosterone levels through a dual mechanism. Specifically, it inhibits enzymes involved in testosterone biosynthesis, such as CYP11A1 and HSD3B2, while upregulating AKR1C2, an enzyme responsible for accelerating testosterone catabolism (Ide et al., 2018). The mechanism of action of curcumin is not limited to the androgen pathway. It has also been demonstrated to inhibit the JNK signaling pathway and exert a regulatory role on gene expression by suppressing epigenetic markers such as H3K4me3 (Wanli et al., 2018). This broad-spectrum activity of curcumin has inspired the development of more potent analogs. Notably, next-generation curcumin analogs such as RL118 and RL121, developed for castration-resistant prostate cancer (CRPC), exhibit stronger effects than the parent compound by inducing G2/M phase cell cycle arrest and promoting apoptosis. These analogs have been found to simultaneously target multiple signaling pathways critical for cell survival, including NF- κ B and AKT/mTOR (Chen et al., 2018).

Role in Combating Glioblastoma

Beyond hormone-related cancers, the effects of curcumin on glioblastoma—one of the most challenging cancer types—have been extensively investigated. Glioblastoma is the most common and aggressive primary brain tumor in adults, and current standard treatments only offer modest improvements in survival, highlighting an urgent need for novel therapeutic approaches (Weathers & Gilbert, 2014). In this context, natural compounds such as curcumin, derived from turmeric, have garnered attention due to their low toxicity profiles and multifaceted anticancer potentials. Preclinical data suggest that curcumin can exert its effects on glioblastoma through various mechanisms, including induction of G2/M phase cell cycle arrest, activation of apoptosis and autophagy, disruption of molecular signaling pathways, and enhancement of the efficacy of existing chemotherapeutic agents (Klinger & Mittal, 2016).

Curcumin has been shown to target treatment-resistant glioblastoma stem cells (GSCs), reducing their viability and proliferative capacity. This effect is attributed to an increase in intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, which activates stress-related pathways such as MAPK, while concurrently suppressing survival pathways including STAT3 and inhibitor of apoptosis proteins (IAPs). This ROS-dependent mechanism suggests that curcumin may serve as a potential therapeutic intervention to prevent glioblastoma recurrence (Gersey et al., 2017).

Broad-Spectrum Effects of Curcumin on Other Cancer Types

The multifaceted mechanisms of curcumin exhibit similar effects across various cancer types located in different regions of the body. Studies have demonstrated that curcumin targets analogous molecular pathways in pancreatic, gastric, hematologic, pulmonary, and cervical cancers. Specifically, curcumin induces apoptosis in pancreatic cancer cells by inhibiting the PI3K/Akt pathway and upregulating Forkhead box O1 (FOXO1) (Zhao et al., 2015), while also promoting cell death through the downregulation of apoptosis inhibitors (Díaz-Osterman et al., 2016). In gastric cancer cells, curcumin modulates proliferation, autophagy, and apoptosis by regulating the PI3K and p53 signaling pathways (Fu et al., 2017) and suppresses cell proliferation, migration, and invasion by inhibiting the Wnt3a/ β -catenin/EMT signaling cascade (Liu et al., 2019). Curcumin's molecular targets in leukemia encompass a broad spectrum (Rafiq et al., 2018). Notably, it induces apoptosis in drug-resistant acute myeloid leukemia (AML) cells by downregulating Bcl-2 expression (Rao et al., 2011) and inhibits invasion while promoting apoptosis through the MAPK/MMP signaling pathway (Zhu et al., 2016).

Curcumin has been found to inhibit the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway (Wang et al., 2018) and EZH2/NOTCH1 signaling (Wu et al., 2016) in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) cells, thereby suppressing tumor growth. Furthermore, it exerts cytotoxic effects through the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Wang et al., 2019) and has demonstrated antineoplastic properties against cancer stem cell subpopulations (Li et al., 2018). In cervical cancer cells, curcumin has been shown to inhibit both the NF- κ B and Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathways (Ghasemi et al., 2019). In one study, treatment with 50 μ M curcumin significantly increased the mRNA expression of differentiation-related genes, including thyroglobulin (TG) and sodium iodide symporter (NIS), in thyroid carcinoma cell lines (TPC-1, FTC-133, BHT-101) (Schwertheim et al., 2017). This treatment also inhibited cell proliferation, induced apoptosis, reduced NF- κ B p65 activity, and caused cell cycle arrest at the G2/M phase (Schwertheim et al., 2017).

Bioavailability Challenges and Innovative Strategies

One of the primary factors limiting the anticancer potential of curcumin is its low bioavailability and poor solubility; therefore, innovative approaches are being developed to overcome these challenges.

Enhancement of Efficacy through Photodynamic Therapy (PDT)

Among these approaches, the combination of curcumin with photodynamic therapy (PDT) has gained significant attention. Although the clinical application of curcumin is limited by its low bioavailability and poor aqueous solubility, its efficacy has been observed to increase when combined with PDT (Fadel et al., 2018; Roos et al., 2019). It has been reported that curcumin at low concentrations exhibits negligible effects when used alone; however, when combined with UVA or visible light, it significantly reduces proliferation and enhances DNA damage in oral squamous cell carcinoma and bladder cancer cells (Beyer et al., 2017; Roos et al., 2019). Light-activated curcumin exerts antitumor effects by inducing cell cycle arrest at

different phases (G0/G1 in RT112 cells and G2/M in TCCSUP and UMUC3 cells) in bladder cancer cell lines (Roos et al., 2019). Similarly, photosensitization of curcumin in glioblastoma multiforme (SNB-19) cells decreased the EC50 value by 6.3-fold and induced apoptosis in over 90% of the cells (Kielbik et al., 2019). The mechanism underlying the combined effect of curcumin and its analogs with PDT is closely related to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). In colorectal cancer cells, irradiation with blue LED light was found to increase ROS accumulation and DNA damage, thereby inhibiting cell proliferation and migration and inducing apoptosis (Yan et al., 2018). The combination of demethoxycurcumin, a more stable curcumin analog, with ultraviolet B (UVB) radiation synergistically induced apoptosis in skin cancer cells (A431 and HaCaT) by promoting ROS production, activating p53 and caspase pathways, and disrupting mitochondrial membrane potential (Xin et al., 2017).

Targeted Therapy via Nanotechnological Delivery Systems

In addition to photodynamic therapy (PDT), nanotechnological delivery systems offer promising outcomes in addressing curcumin's bioavailability issues and enhancing its targeted efficacy. Curcumin-loaded nanoemulsions, when used in combination with PDT, exhibited pronounced phototoxic effects in cervical carcinoma and breast adenocarcinoma (MCF-7) cell lines, reducing viable cell populations to below 5–10% and inducing apoptosis through increased caspase-3/7 activity (De Matos et al., 2018; Machado et al., 2019). Similarly, carriers such as nanoliposomes and gold nanoparticles enhanced the cytotoxic activity of curcumin in hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cells, with nanoliposomes demonstrating superior tumor regression effects (Fadel et al., 2018). Moreover, curcumin encapsulated in biodegradable polymeric PLGA nanoparticles showed potent apoptotic effects in human ovarian adenocarcinoma (SK-OV-3) cells following PDT (Duse et al., 2019). These findings collectively indicate that curcumin, particularly when combined with light activation and nanocarrier systems, represents a promising agent for cancer therapy.

Synergistic Potency in Combination Therapies

Curcumin exerts a robust synergistic effect by modulating key signaling pathways that promote programmed cell death (apoptosis) and inhibit cell survival, thereby significantly enhancing the efficacy of other therapeutic agents. In prostate cancer, the combination of curcumin with docetaxel more effectively suppressed cell proliferation and markedly increased apoptosis compared to monotherapies. This effect has been associated with the regulation of critical cell survival pathways such as PI3K/Akt and NF- κ B (Banerjee et al., 2017). Similarly, studies in gastric cancer have demonstrated that curcumin synergistically enhances the antitumor effects of chemotherapeutic agents, including 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) and oxaliplatin. This combination was reported to activate apoptotic pathways involving Bcl-2/Bax and caspases, while concurrently suppressing COX-2 and NF- κ B signaling cascades (Zhou et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2017). In colorectal cancer cells, curcumin combined with celecoxib, a COX-2 inhibitor, exhibited synergistic growth-inhibitory effects (Lev-Ari et al., 2005). In hepatocellular carcinoma, the combination of curcumin and metformin, an antidiabetic agent, successfully inhibited tumor growth, metastasis, and angiogenesis in both in vitro and in vivo models (Zhang et al., 2018). In bladder cancer cells, curcumin enhanced the antitumor activity of cisplatin by activating the reactive oxygen species (ROS)-mediated ERK1/2 signaling pathway (Park et al., 2016). Additionally, the co-administration of curcumin with quercetin synergistically inhibited proliferation across multiple cancer cell lines (Srivastava & Srivastava, 2019), while its combination with TRAIL potentiated apoptosis through increased caspase-3 activity (Iqbal et al., 2018). The enhancement of ROS production has been confirmed as a fundamental mechanism underlying the tumor-suppressive effects of curcumin derivatives (Nakamae et al., 2019).

Another approach to enhancing the efficacy of curcumin involves the use of drug delivery systems. In Hodgkin lymphoma, curcumin formulated within solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) demonstrated superior antitumor activity compared to the standard formulation and provided additional growth inhibition when combined with chemotherapeutic agents (Guorgui et al., 2018). In addition to phytochemicals like curcumin, the combination potential of newly designed metal-based compounds has also been investigated. For instance, a novel platinum compound exhibited synergistic effects with agents such as curcumin in ovarian cancer models (Arzuman et al., 2014). Similarly, various chemical structures have shown cytotoxic effects on cancer cells; one study reported that a benzimidazole derivative reduced viability in lung and liver cancer cell lines (Bilici & Akkoç, 2025). A notable example highlighting curcumin's potential in combination therapies is the case of Joe Tippens, diagnosed with advanced lung cancer in 2016. Tippens achieved complete remission following a protocol that included fenbendazole, bioavailable curcumin, vitamin E, and CBD oil. Although this case is considered anecdotal from a scientific perspective, it has spurred increased interest in multi-agent protocols involving curcumin (Nguyen et al., 2024). In this context, ongoing research on benzimidazole derivatives, such as fenbendazole used by Tippens, reports potent anticancer effects of newly synthesized analogs in vitro (Bilici & Akkoç, 2025). Collectively, these findings indicate that curcumin holds significant potential as an adjuvant therapy in various cancers by enhancing the efficacy of standard chemotherapeutic agents, promoting apoptosis, and modulating cell survival pathways. These synergistic strategies offer promising prospects for improving therapeutic outcomes while potentially reducing drug dosages and minimizing adverse effects.

Future Perspectives

The presented evidence clearly demonstrates that curcumin, the active constituent of turmeric, possesses a multifaceted and potent potential in cancer therapy. Curcumin exerts its effects across a wide range of cancer types, including breast, prostate, glioblastoma, pancreatic, and lung cancers, through multiple mechanisms such as the induction of apoptosis, cell cycle arrest, inhibition of metastasis, and modulation of critical signaling pathways including NF- κ B, PI3K/Akt, and Wnt/ β -catenin. However, the clinical application of curcumin as a monotherapy remains limited due to its poor bioavailability and low solubility. Innovative strategies such as nanotechnological delivery systems (e.g., liposomes, nanoparticles) and photodynamic therapy (PDT) hold great promise in overcoming these limitations. These approaches not only enhance the targeted efficacy of curcumin but also possess the potential to reduce systemic toxicity. Moreover, curcumin has been shown to synergistically interact with standard chemotherapeutic agents such as cisplatin and paclitaxel, as well as with natural compounds like quercetin, thereby improving treatment efficacy and overcoming drug resistance. In conclusion, despite the challenges associated with the native form of curcumin, its advanced formulations and combination therapies position it as a valuable adjuvant agent in cancer treatment and provide an exciting avenue for future clinical investigations.

Quercetin

Quercetin (chemical name: 3,3',4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone) is a naturally abundant polyphenolic flavonoid belonging to the flavonol subclass. It is widely distributed in numerous fruits, vegetables, and plants, including apples, onions, capers, tea, strawberries, cabbage, broccoli, and citrus fruits (Di Petrillo et al., 2022). Extensive in vitro and in vivo studies have demonstrated quercetin's multifaceted nature. Beyond its direct anticancer effects—such as inhibition of proliferation, angiogenesis, and mitotic processes in cancer cells—quercetin also exerts significant health-promoting functions, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, and immunomodulatory activities (Deng et al., 2025).

As a natural bioflavonoid, quercetin has garnered considerable attention in recent years within cancer research due to its presence in a variety of fruits and vegetables. Scientific evidence indicates that quercetin possesses the potential to inhibit tumor growth and metastasis in several cancer types, including breast, lung, colon, prostate, pancreatic, and ovarian cancers (Vafadar et al., 2020). This broad-spectrum anticancer efficacy is largely attributed to quercetin's capacity to target multiple fundamental molecular mechanisms that drive uncontrolled cancer cell proliferation. Quercetin exerts its effects by inducing programmed cell death (apoptosis), arresting the cell cycle at critical checkpoints, and inhibiting key signaling pathways involved in cancer progression. Moreover, its ability to overcome resistance to conventional chemotherapeutic agents and to act synergistically with these treatments positions quercetin as a promising adjuvant candidate in cancer therapy (Khatoun et al., 2020). This review examines the underlying molecular mechanisms of quercetin's anticancer effects and evaluates its therapeutic potential in light of current scientific evidence.

Mechanisms of Quercetin's Anticancer Activity

One of the primary anticancer mechanisms of quercetin is its ability to arrest cancer cell proliferation by targeting multiple checkpoints within the cell cycle. Numerous studies in the literature have demonstrated that quercetin induces cell cycle arrest predominantly at the G1 and G2/M phases. For instance, quercetin has been shown to cause G1 phase arrest in HepG2 cells through the upregulation of tumor suppressor proteins such as p53, p21, and p27 (Mu et al., 2007). Similarly, another study revealed that quercetin not only induces G1 phase arrest via the p21/pRb/E2F1 pathway but also targets the G2/M phase by downregulating cyclin B1 and CDK1 proteins (Jeong et al., 2008).

In addition to its cell cycle arrest capability, quercetin promotes programmed cell death, or apoptosis, in cancer cells. This apoptotic induction is generally mediated by the downregulation of anti-apoptotic proteins such as Bcl-2 and the concomitant upregulation of pro-apoptotic proteins like Bax. The shift in the Bcl-2/Bax ratio activates the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway, leading to the activation of executioner caspases, including caspase-9 and caspase-3, which ultimately orchestrate controlled cellular self-destruction (Xiang et al., 2014; Yuan et al., 2012; Shen et al., 2012).

Quercetin's anticancer effects are largely mediated through the inhibition of specific signaling pathways that govern cell survival, proliferation, and metastasis.

The Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway, which plays a critical role in cancer progression, is a significant target of quercetin. Studies have demonstrated that quercetin inhibits this pathway at multiple points. Specifically, it has been reported to suppress the transcriptional activity of β -catenin—the key effector protein of the pathway—by preventing its nuclear translocation and stabilization (Mojsin et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2013). As a consequence of this inhibition, the expression of downstream target genes essential for cell cycle progression and survival, such as Cyclin D1, c-Myc, and survivin, is markedly reduced (Srinivasan et al., 2015; Srivastava et al., 2019; Shan et al., 2009). This leads to cell cycle arrest at the G2/M phase and loss of proliferative capacity in cancer cells. Furthermore, quercetin has been shown to reverse epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), a process that confers migratory ability to cancer cells, thereby reducing their metastatic potential (Srinivasan et al., 2015).

Another central mechanism underlying quercetin's antitumor effects involves the phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K)/Akt signaling pathway. Quercetin's structural similarity to the commercial PI3K inhibitor LY294002 has sparked considerable interest in this pathway (Gulati et al., 2006). Consistently, multiple studies have demonstrated that quercetin effectively suppresses the phosphorylation of Akt (p-Akt), a pivotal component of the pathway, across various cancer types (Granato et al., 2017; Gulati et al., 2006; Xiang et al., 2014; Yuan et al.,

2012; Shen et al., 2012). This inhibition triggers the apoptotic mechanisms described above and induces cell cycle arrest at the G0/G1 phase (Xiang et al., 2014; Yuan et al., 2012). Additionally, suppression of the PI3K/Akt pathway by quercetin disrupts cancer cell energy metabolism; quercetin has been reported to downregulate glucose transporters (GLUT1) and key glycolytic enzymes, thereby impairing nutrient supply within the tumor microenvironment. It also decreases the expression of metastasis-associated proteins such as matrix metalloproteinases MMP-2 and MMP-9 (Jia et al., 2018).

The Janus kinase/signal transducer and activator of transcription (JAK/STAT) signaling pathway is also among the key targets of quercetin. In various cancer types, quercetin has been shown to inhibit the activation of JAK2 and STAT3/5 (Wu et al., 2019; Luo et al., 2016). Specifically, in HER2-positive breast cancer, quercetin has been reported to reduce the levels of phosphorylated JAK1 and phosphorylated STAT3 (Seo et al., 2016). In lung cancer cells, this inhibition manifests as the downregulation of the IL-6/STAT3 axis (Mukherjee & Khuda-Bukhsh, 2015). Moreover, quercetin has been demonstrated to decrease the nuclear translocation of STAT3 (Seo et al., 2016). Inhibition of this pathway can trigger distinct apoptotic mechanisms depending on the cancer type. For instance, in HER2-positive breast cancer, quercetin induces extrinsic apoptosis (Seo et al., 2016), whereas in lung cancer, it initiates mitochondrial-mediated intrinsic apoptosis (Mukherjee & Khuda-Bukhsh, 2015). Additionally, this mechanism exerts anti-metastatic effects by suppressing the secretion of proteins such as matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9), which is regulated by STAT3 and plays a role in cancer dissemination (Seo et al., 2016).

Overcoming Chemoresistance and Synergistic Effects

One of the most promising attributes of quercetin is its potential to overcome chemoresistance in cancer cells and enhance the efficacy of standard treatments. Numerous studies have demonstrated that quercetin can reverse chemoresistance through various mechanisms. For instance, in doxorubicin-resistant breast cancer cells, quercetin was found to restore sensitivity by suppressing the expression of genes associated with cell migration and resistance (Almohammad Aljabr et al., 2024). Similarly, in colorectal cancer cells, quercetin increased sensitivity to 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) by regulating mitochondrial dynamics mediated by Drp-1 and inhibiting protective autophagy (Li et al., 2024).

Quercetin exhibits robust synergistic effects when combined with both conventional chemotherapeutic agents and other natural compounds. When used in combination with drugs such as cisplatin, quercetin significantly enhances apoptosis by inhibiting the NF- κ B signaling pathway (Li et al., 2019). Furthermore, co-administration with natural compounds like resveratrol, curcumin, hyperoside, and sulforaphane has demonstrated greater inhibition of cell proliferation and suppression of cancer stem cell propagation at substantially lower doses compared to monotherapies (Singh et al., 2020; Appari et al., 2014). The underlying mechanisms for these synergistic effects frequently involve the targeting of common signaling pathways such as PI3K/Akt, as well as oncogenic microRNAs including miR-21 and miR-27a (Yang et al., 2015; Li et al., 2014; Del Follo-Martinez et al., 2013).

To overcome limitations such as the low bioavailability of quercetin, nanotechnology-based delivery systems have been developed. Strategies including the loading of quercetin and curcumin into apoferritin nanoparticles, as well as the targeted delivery of quercetin in combination with gemcitabine using hyaluronic acid-coated nanoparticles, have demonstrated more targeted effects at substantially lower doses compared to free drug formulations (Mansourizadeh et al., 2020; Serri et al., 2019). Such approaches significantly enhance the future clinical potential of quercetin-based combination therapies.

Additional Therapeutic Roles and Potential

Quercetin exhibits significant potential to enhance the efficacy of anticancer drugs while simultaneously mitigating their adverse effects when used in combination therapies (Rauf et al., 2018; Sahyon et al., 2019). This multifaceted role positions quercetin as a critical benchmark in the development of novel therapeutic agents. This is particularly evident in recent studies investigating promising benzimidazole derivatives, wherein the anticancer and antioxidant capacities of new molecules are evaluated with quercetin serving as the “gold standard” (Bilici & Akkoç, 2025). Notably, one such study reported that certain newly developed compounds provided protective effects against oxidative damage comparable to or exceeding those of quercetin (Argirova et al., 2021). These examples underscore quercetin’s dual function in contemporary cancer research, acting both as a therapeutic adjunct and an indispensable scientific reference for the evaluation of novel drug candidates.

Quercetin’s synergistic potential is not confined solely to anticancer applications; it also assumes a protective role against toxin-induced organ damage. Abdel-Daim et al. (2019) demonstrated that the combination of quercetin and curcumin synergistically reversed pesticide-induced neurohepatic injury almost completely through antioxidant and anti-inflammatory mechanisms. Similarly, Al Humayed et al. (2019) reported that the combination of quercetin and resveratrol preserved cellular ultrastructure and effectively suppressed oxidative stress in acetaminophen-induced acute liver injury. Collectively, these findings strongly underscore the robust therapeutic potential of quercetin-based combinations, both in nanotechnology-enhanced cancer therapies and in organ protection against toxicity, highlighting their promising prospects for future clinical applications.

Conclusion and Future Perspectives

The evidence presented in this review clearly demonstrates that quercetin, a natural flavonoid, possesses a multifaceted and potent anticancer potential. Rather than targeting a single molecule, quercetin acts as a "multi-target" agent by concurrently modulating several critical signaling pathways essential for cancer cell survival, proliferation, and metastasis, including Wnt/ β -catenin, PI3K/Akt, and JAK/STAT. Such a strategy may offer a significant advantage over conventional therapies that focus on single pathways, particularly in addressing the complexity and heterogeneity inherent to cancer.

The fundamental anticancer mechanisms of quercetin, including the induction of apoptosis, cell cycle arrest, and inhibition of metastasis, have been consistently validated in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models. More importantly, quercetin’s ability to overcome resistance to conventional chemotherapeutic agents and to exert synergistic effects with these drugs holds significant promise for clinical applications. This potential is further enhanced by advancements in nanotechnology-based delivery systems that improve quercetin’s bioavailability. However, despite these encouraging preclinical findings, there remains a paucity of comprehensive clinical trials evaluating the effects of quercetin on cancer treatment in humans (Soofiyan et al., 2021). Therefore, future research must prioritize determining the optimal dosing, safety profile, and pharmacokinetics of quercetin in human subjects. Of particular urgency is the conduction of well-designed, randomized controlled clinical trials assessing quercetin as an adjunct to standard chemotherapy regimens. Such studies are critical to facilitate the translation of quercetin from bench to bedside, potentially leading to more effective, less toxic, and more integrative therapeutic strategies in the fight against cancer.

Gallic acid

(GA) is an endogenous plant polyphenol abundantly found in tea, grapes, strawberries, various other fruits, and wine (Jagdish Singh et al., 2004). Known to modulate multiple

pharmacological and biochemical pathways, GA exhibits potent antibacterial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antimutagenic, antioxidant, and anticancer properties. Indeed, the anticancer activity of GA has been demonstrated across a wide range of cancer types, including lung, prostate, breast, leukemia, gastric, colorectal, cervical, and esophageal cancers (Jiang et al., 2022).

Core Anticancer Mechanisms of Gallic Acid

One of the most prominent mechanisms underlying the anticancer effects of gallic acid (GA) is the induction of apoptosis (programmed cell death) via reactive oxygen species (ROS). In a study conducted on prostate cancer (LNCaP) cells, GA was shown to generate hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and superoxide radicals ($\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$) through autoxidation. The resulting elevated intracellular ROS levels led to the loss of mitochondrial membrane potential, release of cytochrome c into the cytoplasm, and subsequent activation of caspases-3, -8, and -9, thereby initiating apoptotic cell death (Russel et al., 2012). Similarly, in chronic myeloid leukemia (K562) cells, GA induced apoptosis by activating the mitochondrial pathway—evidenced by disruption of the Bcl-2/Bax ratio and cytochrome c leakage—and the death receptor pathway via caspase-8 activation (Reddy et al., 2012). This ROS-mediated apoptotic effect has been corroborated in various cancer types. For instance, Subramanian et al. (2016) demonstrated that gallic acid alone inhibited the growth of HCT-15 colon cancer cells and induced apoptosis in a ROS-dependent manner. GA treatment was observed to arrest cells in the sub-G1 phase of the cell cycle, decrease mitochondrial membrane potential, and cause apoptotic morphological changes such as cell shrinkage.

The anticancer efficacy of gallic acid (GA) extends beyond the induction of cell death, also targeting the metastatic potential of cancer cells. In human melanoma cells, GA was found to suppress the expression of matrix metalloproteinases MMP-2 and MMP-9 at both protein and gene levels, which play critical roles in cancer invasion. This effect was reported to occur via inhibition of the Ras/p-ERK signaling pathway, highlighting GA's antimetastatic potential (Chyi et al., 2011). Similarly, in cervical cancer cell lines (HeLa and HTB-35), GA significantly reduced cell invasion and tumor-induced angiogenesis (tube formation). The underlying mechanism was attributed to the downregulation of ADAM17 expression and consequent suppression of EGFR, Akt, and Erk signaling pathways (Zhao and Hu, 2013). Moreover, GA was shown to inhibit migration and invasion in oral squamous cell carcinoma (Guimarães, 2016) and to impede angiogenesis—crucial for tumor nourishment—in ovarian cancer by modulating the PTEN/AKT/HIF-1 α signaling axis (He, 2016).

Additionally, gallic acid (GA) interferes with the cell cycle, which is responsible for the uncontrolled proliferation of cancer cells. In chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) cells, GA was shown to induce cell cycle arrest at the G0/G1 phase by upregulating cell cycle inhibitors such as p21 and p27, while downregulating progression-promoting proteins including cyclin D and cyclin E. Similarly, in colorectal cancer cells, GA decreased cell viability in a dose- and time-dependent manner, caused G0/G1 phase cell cycle arrest, and induced apoptosis via caspase-3 activation. During this process, GA also inhibited critical transcription factors involved in cancer progression, such as NF- κ B and AP-1 (Forester, 2014).

Selective Toxicity Against Cancer Cells

One of the most notable characteristics of gallic acid (GA) is its selective cytotoxicity toward cancer cells compared to normal cells. Studies have demonstrated that GA induces apoptosis selectively in cancerous cells of the brain, liver, and ovary, while exerting minimal effects on the corresponding normal cells (Hsu, 2016; Sun, 2015; He, 2016). In glioblastoma, this selective effect is mediated by the induction of intracellular calcium (Ca^{2+}) signaling, which subsequently triggers reactive oxygen species (ROS) production (Hsu, 2016).

Synergistic Effects: Combination with Other Therapies

Scientific studies have demonstrated that the true potential of gallic acid (GA) lies in its synergistic effects when combined with other treatment modalities. For instance, Moghtaderi et al. (2018) reported that the combination of gallic acid and curcumin markedly inhibited cell proliferation in the triple-negative breast cancer cell line MDA-MB-231. This combination was shown to exert its effect by elevating intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels and inducing apoptosis. Protein analyses revealed that this effect was associated with a decrease in the anti-apoptotic protein Bcl-2 and an increase in pro-apoptotic proteins such as Bax, caspase-3, and PARP.

The synergistic potential of GA with existing chemotherapeutic agents has also been investigated. Yang et al. (2022) demonstrated that GA enhanced the anticancer efficacy of Temozolomide (TMZ), a drug used in the treatment of malignant glioma. The combination of GA and TMZ more effectively inhibited glioma cell viability and promoted apoptosis compared to either agent alone. This synergistic effect was linked to the downregulation of Bcl-2 expression, suppression of the Akt survival signaling pathway, and activation of the p38 MAPK stress pathway. Interestingly, the study also observed that GA attenuated TMZ-induced ROS production, suggesting that GA may exert differential mechanisms of action depending on the cellular context.

Similarly, in small cell lung cancer (SCLC), gallic acid was found to synergistically enhance the efficacy of the standard chemotherapeutic agent cisplatin. This effect was mediated through increased ROS generation and activation of the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway by upregulating pro-apoptotic proteins including Bax, Apaf-1, DIABLO, and p53 (Wang, 2016).

These findings strongly support the notion that gallic acid (GA) functions not merely as a standalone agent but as a valuable adjuvant molecule capable of enhancing the efficacy of existing cancer therapies. For example, treatment with GA following low-level laser irradiation (LLLI) was shown to increase cancer cell death by inducing apoptosis and ferroptosis, while simultaneously protecting normal cells (Khorsandi et al., 2020). Similarly, GA was reported to potentiate the efficacy of the standard chemotherapeutic agent cisplatin against non-small cell lung cancer cells via modulation of the JAK/STAT3 signaling pathway (Zhang et al., 2019). Furthermore, when combined with another natural compound, curcumin, GA elicited a significantly stronger cytotoxic effect in aggressive breast cancer cells (Moghtaderi et al., 2018).

Efficacy Against Drug-Resistant Cancer Cells

One of the most notable findings in this area is the effectiveness of gallic acid (GA) against drug-resistant cancer cells. In imatinib-resistant chronic myeloid leukemia cells (IR-K562), GA demonstrated significantly greater potency at much lower concentrations compared to non-resistant cells (IC_{50} : 4 μ M vs. 33 μ M). This enhanced efficacy has been attributed to GA's ability to inhibit key resistance-associated targets, including the BCR/ABL tyrosine kinase, NF- κ B, and COX-2 (Reddy et al., 2012).

Gallic Acid as a Multifaceted Anticancer Agent

In summary, the accumulated evidence strongly supports gallic acid (GA) as a multifaceted anticancer agent. GA exerts its effects through diverse mechanisms, including the induction of apoptosis via reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation, inhibition of metastasis and invasion, cell cycle arrest, and targeting of drug-resistant cancer cells. Its mechanism of action involves modulation of ROS production, mitochondrial pathways, and key signaling proteins such as Bcl-2, Bax, Akt, and MAPK. These findings suggest that GA possesses significant potential as a standalone therapeutic or in combination with existing

chemotherapeutic agents for cancer treatment. However, the translation of this potential into clinical applications necessitates further validation through advanced *in vivo* animal studies and human clinical trials (Subramanian et al., 2015).

Conclusion and Evaluation

In conclusion, the presented scientific data clearly demonstrates that gallic acid, abundantly found in natural sources like tea and grapes, possesses a multifaceted and potent anti-cancer potential. This potential stems from gallic acid's ability to combat cancer cells on multiple fronts. Its primary mechanisms of action include inducing programmed cell death (apoptosis) by generating reactive oxygen species (ROS), inhibiting the spread (metastasis), invasion, and the formation of new blood vessels (angiogenesis) that cancer cells need to nourish themselves, and arresting the cell cycle that drives their uncontrolled proliferation.

One of the most remarkable features of gallic acid is its selective toxicity, targeting cancer cells without harming normal cells, and its effectiveness even against cancer cells that have developed resistance to standard treatments. Furthermore, rather than being a standalone therapeutic agent, gallic acid has been proven to be a synergistic force that enhances the efficacy of existing chemotherapeutic drugs like cisplatin and temozolomide, as well as other natural compounds like curcumin. This makes it a valuable candidate as an "adjuvant molecule" to support current cancer therapies.

All these findings position gallic acid as a promising molecule in cancer therapy. However, for these impressive laboratory findings to be translated into tangible treatments for patients, verifying its potential through comprehensive *in vivo* animal experiments and subsequent human clinical trials is the critical next step.

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